

Theoretical insight on the treatment of β -hexachlorocyclohexane waste through alkaline dehydrochlorination

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Table S1. Relative Gibbs free energies of activation at 25 °C and 1 atm (kJ mol⁻¹) for the β -HCH + HO⁻ reaction (starting from the pre-reactive complex) at different theoretical levels and medium models by using the 6-311++G(d,p) basis set.

Theoretical level	Medium model	Activation energy
HF	gas phase	25.8
HF	IEFPCM	41.2
HF	CPCM	42.4
BLYP	gas phase	8.1
BLYP	IEFPCM	5.5
BLYP	CPCM	9.4
B3LYP	gas phase	4.0
B3LYP	IEFPCM	15.5
B3LYP	CPCM	15.4
M062X	gas phase	3.9
M062X	IEFPCM	11.7
M062X	CPCM	9.3

Table S2. Electronic energies and Gibbs free energies (Hartree) at 25 °C and 1 atm of both pre-reactive complex and TS involved in the β -HCH + HO⁻ reaction at different theoretical levels and medium models by using the 6-311++G(d,p) basis set.

Structure	Theoretical level	Medium model	Electronic energy (Ha)	Gibbs free energy (Ha)
pre-reactive complex	HF	gas phase	-3063.27777225	-3063.186166
pre-reactive complex	HF	IEFPCM	-3063.36190867	-3063.271818
pre-reactive complex	HF	CPCM	-3063.36224780	-3063.272747
pre-reactive complex	BLYP	gas phase	-3069.33862011	-3069.266407
pre-reactive complex	BLYP	IEFPCM	-3069.41584673	-3069.341768
pre-reactive complex	BLYP	CPCM	-3069.41601372	-3069.343290
pre-reactive complex	B3LYP	gas phase	-3069.56766407	-3069.488424
pre-reactive complex	B3LYP	IEFPCM	-3069.64653648	-3069.568193
pre-reactive complex	B3LYP	CPCM	-3069.64682823	-3069.568463
pre-reactive complex	M06-2X	gas phase	-3069.28700225	-3069.203858
pre-reactive complex	M06-2X	IEFPCM	-3069.36650603	-3069.285279
pre-reactive complex	M06-2X	CPCM	-3069.36652872	-3069.284443
TS	HF	gas phase	-3063.26221329	-3063.176346
TS	HF	IEFPCM	-3063.34138934	-3063.256140
TS	HF	CPCM	-3063.34164571	-3063.256585
TS	BLYP	gas phase	-3069.33296334	-3069.263316
TS	BLYP	IEFPCM	-3069.40846528	-3069.339687
TS	BLYP	CPCM	-3069.40871672	-3069.339725
TS	B3LYP	gas phase	-3069.56004841	-3069.486915
TS	B3LYP	IEFPCM	-3069.63619297	-3069.562283
TS	B3LYP	CPCM	-3069.63643368	-3069.562594
TS	M06-2X	gas phase	-3069.28055526	-3069.202360
TS	M06-2X	IEFPCM	-3069.36043423	-3069.280814
TS	M06-2X	CPCM	-3069.36061728	-3069.280908

Table S3. Relative Gibbs free energies relative to non-interacting reactants (not in parentheses) and relative to the most stable pre-reactive complex of the corresponding stage (in parentheses) for all structures at CPCM(water)/M06-2X/6-311++G(d,p) level (kJ mol⁻¹)^a.

Stage	Reaction step	Reactants	Pre-reactive complex	TS	Reaction Intermediate	Second TS	Post-reactive complex	Products
First	β -HCH $\rightarrow$ 1 : 1,2	0.0 (15.5)	-20.4 (0.0)	-11.1 (9.3)			-192.5 (-177.1)	-213.2 (-197.7)
Second	1 $\rightarrow$ 2 : 1,2 (C4)	-213.2 (28.3)	-241.5 (0.0)	-206.7 (34.8)			-408.7 (-167.2)	-440.3 (-198.8)
Second	1 $\rightarrow$ 2 : 1,2 (C4)	-213.2 (28.3)	-241.5 (0.0)	-207.2 (34.3)	-219.9 (21.6)	-213.4 (28.1)	-393.3 (-151.8)	-440.3 (-198.8)
Second	1 $\rightarrow$ 3 : 1,2 (C4)	-213.2 (28.3)	_{-b}	_{-b}			_{-b}	-431.8 (-190.3)
Second	1 $\rightarrow$ 4 : 1,2 (C5)	-213.2 (28.3)	_{-b}	_{-b}			_{-b}	-433.0 (-191.5)
Second	1 $\rightarrow$ 5 : 1,2 (C5)	-213.2 (28.3)	-241.5 (0.0)	-208.1 (33.4)			-389.5 (-148.0)	-438.3 (-196.8)
Second	1 $\rightarrow$ 5 : 1,2 (C3)	-213.2 (28.3)	-241.5 (0.0)	-231.9 (9.6)			-397.3 (-155.9)	-438.3 (-196.8)
Second	1 $\rightarrow$ 5 : 1,4 (C3)	-213.2 (28.3)	-241.5 (0.0)	-237.3 (4.2)			-375.6 (-134.1)	-438.3 (-196.8)
Second	1 $\rightarrow$ 6 : 1,4 (C6)	-213.2 (28.3)	-241.5 (0.0)	-237.2 (4.3)			-372.8 (-131.3)	-414.5 (-173.0)
Second	1 $\rightarrow$ 7 : 1,2 (C6)	-213.2 (28.3)	_{-b}	_{-b}			_{-b}	-428.6 (-187.1)
Third	2 $\rightarrow$ 1,2,4-TCB: 1,2	-440.3 (-5.1)	-435.2 (0.0)	-437.7 (-2.4)			-740.4 (-303.4)	-770.3 (-31.7)
Third	3 $\rightarrow$ 1,2,4-TCB: 1,4	-431.8 (3.4)	_{-b}	_{-b}			_{-b}	-770.3 (-31.7)
Third	4 $\rightarrow$ 1,2,3-TCB: 1,4	-433.0 (2.2)	-432.7 (2.6)	-431.6 (3.5)			-722.1 (-287.0)	-763.4 (-24.8)
Third	4 $\rightarrow$ 1,3,5-TCB: 1,4	-433.0 (2.2)	_{-b}	_{-b}			_{-b}	-775.6 (-37.0)
Third	5 $\rightarrow$ 1,2,4-TCB: 1,2	-438.3 (-3.0)	-432.9 (2.3)	-434.2 (1.0)			-740.4 (-303.0)	-770.3 (-31.7)
Third	5 $\rightarrow$ 1,3,5-TCB: 1,2	-438.3 (-3.0)	-432.9 (2.3)	-429.2 (6.0)			-744.7 (-309.5)	-775.6 (-37.0)
Third	6 $\rightarrow$ 1,2,3-TCB: 1,2	-414.5 (20.7)	-422.8 (12.4)	-409.4 (21.2)			-726.9 (-296.3)	-763.4 (-24.8)
Third	6 $\rightarrow$ 1,2,4-TCB: 1,2	-414.5 (20.7)	-422.8 (12.4)	-424.2 (10.9)			-745.0 (-309.8)	-770.3 (-31.7)
Third	7 $\rightarrow$ 1,2,4-TCB: 1,2	-428.6 (6.6)	-417.2 (18.1)	-418.2 (17.0)			-740.4 (-306.3)	-770.3 (-31.7)

^a Free energy values of co-reactants (hydroxide anion) and co-products (water, chloride anion) have been included in the calculated energies.

^b Structure not located.

Table S4. Electronic energies and Gibbs free energies at 25 °C and 1 atm of computed structures at CPCM(water)/M06-2X/6-311++G(d,p) level.

Structure	Electronic Energy (Ha)	Gibbs Free Energy (Ha)
β -HCH (all-equatorial conformer)	-2993.42853793	-2993.351230
β -HCH (all-axial conformer)	-2993.41583073	-2993.339754
hydroxide anion (HO ⁻)	-75.91807776	-75.925439
water (H ₂ O)	-76.42901303	-76.425146
chloride anion (Cl ⁻)	-460.38000994	-460.395033
pre-reactive complex β -HCH $\rightarrow$ 1: 1,2	-3069.36138250	-3069.282555
TS β -HCH $\rightarrow$ 1: 1,2	-3069.36061728	-3069.280908
post-reactive complex β -HCH $\rightarrow$ 1: 1,2	-3069.42794522	-3069.350002
<i>rel</i> -(3 <i>R</i> ,4 <i>S</i> ,5 <i>R</i> ,6 <i>S</i>)-1,3,4,5,6-pentachlorocyclohex-1-ene (1)	-2532.59917771	-2532.537691
pre-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 2: 1,2 (C4) E2 path	-2608.53187300	-2608.462786
TS 1 $\rightarrow$ 2: 1,2 (C4) E2 path	-2608.52430242	-2608.460666
post-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 2: 1,2 (C4) E2 path	-2608.60195478	-2608.537582
pre-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 2: 1,2 (C4) E1cB path	-2608.53187287	-2608.462798
TS 1 $\rightarrow$ 2: 1,2 (C4) E1cB path	-2608.52421001	-2608.460839
Reaction intermediate 1 $\rightarrow$ 2: 1,2 (C4) E1cB path	-2608.52977836	-2608.465690
Second TS 1 $\rightarrow$ 2: 1,2 (C4) E1cB path	-2608.52975746	-2608.463221
post-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 2: 1,2 (C4) E1cB path	-2608.59534017	-2608.531731
<i>trans</i> -1,4,5,6-tetrachlorocyclohexa-1,3-diene (2)	-2071.77870592	-2071.729451
pre-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 3: 1,2 (C4)	-	-
TS 1 $\rightarrow$ 3 1,2 (C4)	- ^a	- ^a
post-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 3: 1,2 (C4)	-	-
<i>trans</i> -1,3,4,6-tetrachlorocyclohexa-1,4-diene (3)	-2071.77515425	-2071.726214
pre-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 4: 1,2 (C5)	-	-
TS 1 $\rightarrow$ 4: 1,2 (C5)	- ^a	- ^a
post-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 4: 1,2 (C5)	-	-
<i>trans</i> -1,3,5,6-tetrachlorocyclohexa-1,4-diene (4)	-2071.77489377	-2071.726683
pre-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 5: 1,2 (C5)	-2608.54064488	-2608.473908
TS 1 $\rightarrow$ 5: 1,2 (C5)	-2608.52518400	-2608.461202
post-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 5: 1,2 (C5)	-2608.59549036	-2608.530268
pre-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 5: 1,2 (C3)	-2608.54064488	-2608.473908
TS 1 $\rightarrow$ 5: 1,2 (C3)	-2608.53602484	-2608.470253
post-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 5: 1,2 (C3)	-2608.54064488	-2608.473908
pre-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 5: 1,4 (C3)	-2608.54064488	-2608.473908
TS 1 $\rightarrow$ 5: 1,4 (C3)	-2608.53729252	-2608.472314
post-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 5: 1,4 (C3)	-2608.58846835	-2608.524990
<i>trans</i> -1,3,5,6-tetrachlorocyclohexa-1,3-diene (5)	-2071.77772237	-2071.728679
pre-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 6: 1,4 (C6)	-2608.54064488	-2608.473908
TS 1 $\rightarrow$ 6: 1,4 (C6)	-2608.53718105	-2608.472289
post-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 6: 1,4 (C6)	-2608.58714469	-2608.523935
<i>trans</i> -1,2,5,6-tetrachlorocyclohexa-1,3-diene (6)	-2071.76803222	-2071.719636
pre-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 7: 1,4 (C6)	-	-
TS 1 $\rightarrow$ 7: 1,4 (C6)	- ^a	- ^a
post-reactive complex 1 $\rightarrow$ 7: 1,4 (C6)	-	-
<i>trans</i> -1,2,5,6-tetrachlorocyclohexa-1,3-diene (7)	-2071.77379002	-2071.724986
pre-reactive complex 2 $\rightarrow$ 1,2,4-TCB	-2147.70731662	-2147.652957
TS 2 $\rightarrow$ 1,2,4-TCB	-2147.70573048	-2147.653882
post-reactive complex 2 $\rightarrow$ 1,2,4-TCB	-2147.82167425	-2147.768512
pre-reactive complex 3 $\rightarrow$ 1,2,4-TCB	-	-
TS 3 $\rightarrow$ 1,2,4-TCB	- ^a	- ^a
post-reactive complex 3 $\rightarrow$ 1,2,4-TCB	-	-
pre-reactive complex 4 $\rightarrow$ 1,2,3-TCB	-2147.70517924	-2147.651980
TS 4 $\rightarrow$ 1,2,3-TCB	-2147.70516515	-2147.651589

post-reactive complex 4 →1,2,3-TCB	-2147.81203912	-2147.762244
pre-reactive complex 4 →1,3,5-TCB	-	-
TS 4 →1,3,5-TCB	- ^a	- ^a
post-reactive complex 4 →1,3,5-TCB	-	-
pre-reactive complex 5 →1,2,4-TCB	-2147.70607241	-2147.652084
TS 5 →1,2,4-TCB	-2147.70436932	-2147.652569
post-reactive complex 5 →1,2,4-TCB	-2147.82119167	-2147.768363
pre-reactive complex 5 →1,3,5-TCB	-2147.70607241	-2147.652084
TS 5 →1,3,5-TCB	-2147.70178331	-2147.650669
post-reactive complex 5 →1,3,5-TCB	-2147.82368645	-2147.770839
pre-reactive complex 6 →1,2,3-TCB	-2147.69696908	-2147.643642
TS 6 →1,2,3-TCB	-2147.69684443	-2147.644863
post-reactive complex 6 →1,2,3-TCB	-2147.82134279	-2147.765795
pre-reactive complex 6 →1,2,4-TCB	-2147.70382443	-2147.648214
TS 6 →1,2,4-TCB	-2147.69964570	-2147.648772
post-reactive complex 6 →1,2,4-TCB	-2147.82134279	-2147.770930
pre-reactive complex 7 →1,2,4-TCB	-2147.70103386	-2147.646077
TS 7 →1,2,4-TCB	-2147.69734417	-2147.646456
post-reactive complex 7 →1,2,4-TCB	-2147.82109293	-2147.769585
1,2,3-TCB	-1610.99581172	-1610.957765
1,2,4-TCB	-1610.99843290	-1610.960407
1,3,5-TCB	-1611.00016806	-1610.962423
1,3-dichlorocyclohex-2-en-1-yl localized anion	-1153.27075300	-1153.190449
TS 1,3-dichlorocyclohex-2-en-1-yl delocalized anion	-1153.26445648	-1153.184823
1,2-dichlorocyclohex-2-en-1-yl anion	-1153.27381173	-1153.193665

^a Structure not located.

Table S5. Cartesian coordinates of both pre-reactive complex and TS involved in the first stage of β -HCH elimination as calculated at different theoretical levels and medium models.

pre-reactive complex, gas-phase/HF/6-311++G(d,p)

C	1.3991948019	-0.3548567970	-0.3480973542
C	0.3815270484	-1.4001067782	0.1138104224
H	1.5065610493	-0.3883779895	-1.4230720911
C1	0.8381897076	-3.0008790658	-0.6082328615
C1	3.0260238060	-0.7641232868	0.3008313497
H	0.3945777800	-1.4737110828	1.1917252666
O	-0.0395432175	0.0225817544	2.5329389725
H	-0.0431213630	0.0439280234	3.4723100785
C	-1.4318436483	0.3666719655	0.0843301286
H	-1.5222644943	0.3951329130	1.1607037429
C	-0.4059334228	1.4037217948	-0.3777919099
H	-0.4242606772	1.4926047685	-1.4548215441
C	1.0052950594	1.0543539181	0.0995262935
H	1.0557977619	1.1244643293	1.1764289753
C	-1.0261380617	-1.0386834946	-0.3650249936
H	-1.0861766089	-1.1183402490	-1.4412798743
C1	-2.2073729043	-2.2409106360	0.2629600333
C1	-3.0320053525	0.7694026106	-0.6701155986
C1	-0.8681746207	3.0296861390	0.2370121623
C1	2.1680793565	2.2351521633	-0.6394301986

pre-reactive complex, IEFPCM/HF/6-311++G(d,p)

C	1.2743432532	0.7101100617	-0.4147180153
C	1.2521816627	-0.7462252497	0.0536696520
H	1.3777888912	0.7648918955	-1.4871556711
C1	2.6905966269	-1.6036039248	-0.6159672805
C1	2.7310240889	1.5263285682	0.2605726140
H	1.3131839967	-0.7811353496	1.1290436017
O	-0.0226649291	0.0258032998	2.7860441207
H	0.0066501203	-0.0203125354	3.7268185192
C	-1.2705133350	-0.7121092276	0.0501110570
H	-1.3362107807	-0.7474074818	1.1253370852
C	-1.2520128079	0.7451405172	-0.4158619302
H	-1.3535714724	0.8054340924	-1.4881815088
C	0.0210022238	1.4549340104	0.0496345790
H	0.0214989497	1.5280978305	1.1248744572
C	-0.0184036331	-1.4597125005	-0.4131743133
H	-0.0179633523	-1.5780131315	-1.4855949921
C1	-0.0424348887	-3.1282253430	0.2647602277
C1	-2.7294970601	-1.5290755314	-0.6261248461
C1	-2.6862538329	1.5997910247	0.2601432928
C1	0.0441442790	3.1272959750	-0.6252536490

pre-reactive complex, CPCM/HF/6-311++G(d,p)

C	1.2022017293	-0.8337589517	-0.3992533633
C	-0.1236634405	-1.4530788812	0.0476316520
H	1.3167917324	-0.9038364820	-1.4696209370
C1	-0.2531341512	-3.1211065171	-0.6258605547
C1	2.5632657502	-1.7838588136	0.3007763590
H	-0.1440657311	-1.5245623092	1.1227789522
O	-0.0411895512	0.0091044722	2.7900342453
H	-0.0282456470	-0.0333914443	3.7313357151
C	-1.1997982349	0.8285098069	0.0321121530
H	-1.2756840480	0.8703226977	1.1063463609

C	0.1240896715	1.4532173698	-0.4135452062
H	0.1489759014	1.5760052384	-1.4850568977
C	1.3139961127	0.6195565869	0.0669469682
H	1.3649508221	0.6501683627	1.1430152550
C	-1.3163348459	-0.6243471878	-0.4343853460
H	-1.4110279961	-0.6766190764	-1.5077804671
C1	-2.8342907417	-1.3356020306	0.2251763594
C1	-2.5647715585	1.7821117937	-0.6605245334
C1	0.2521800513	3.1148910670	0.2703828484
C1	2.8363751755	1.3330072986	-0.5849855628

pre-reactive complex, gas-phase/BLYP/6-311++G(d,p)

C	1.4154027386	-0.3595985079	-0.3734742992
C	0.3997070502	-1.4138961007	0.1169025088
H	1.5074574302	-0.3882281859	-1.4663078729
C1	0.8570401741	-3.0704832511	-0.6231862773
C1	3.1084568235	-0.7870278104	0.2354328939
H	0.4256004397	-1.4795434666	1.2194616884
O	0.1388294038	-0.0200343207	2.5190314656
H	-0.3955703378	0.1357850362	3.3176167251
C	-1.4225376659	0.3650897507	0.1087730956
H	-1.5019355990	0.3904480375	1.2062601724
C	-0.3969161092	1.4150854478	-0.3595188907
H	-0.4366673524	1.5394113350	-1.4482215872
C	1.0273115615	1.0560811864	0.1056592647
H	1.0821681024	1.1095608140	1.2083715074
C	-1.0241752789	-1.0518454569	-0.3474743455
H	-1.1212761026	-1.1518306977	-1.4350347613
C1	-2.2346079518	-2.2832640836	0.3311758320
C1	-3.0897612195	0.7844600034	-0.6673143607
C1	-0.8702936384	3.0815498620	0.3046228963
C1	2.2201795314	2.2859914085	-0.6480646553

pre-reactive complex, IEFPCM/BLYP/6-311++G(d,p)

C	-1.407772476649	-0.381796146560	-0.427700919175
C	-1.035127379041	1.033857190882	0.060705175046
H	-1.523434735094	-0.411598541398	-1.516257292614
C1	-2.256665830869	2.256953114482	-0.614983700454
C1	-3.078835032520	-0.835667218943	0.234826922773
H	-1.080672070264	1.069803047887	1.159052317614
O	-0.180947637576	-0.057425185281	2.712169524056
H	0.523638809380	0.067416332717	3.374219233442
C	1.422921083752	0.387306215529	0.057918939717
H	1.494740110707	0.405581044101	1.152490284554
C	1.050584205926	-1.034675045217	-0.409319515111
H	1.156356023896	-1.135948564047	-1.494106001466
C	-0.369114054161	-1.414518187497	0.058213321335
H	-0.389068857341	-1.466436573085	1.157885367624
C	0.381335891668	1.425955056338	-0.406657452858
H	0.419640497214	1.567679615765	-1.491385109572
C1	0.819804248959	3.083230850472	0.301439929867
C1	3.085444153029	0.840203675649	-0.636610945730
C1	2.268636191241	-2.242004567432	0.297908685398
C1	-0.803613142259	-3.087204114361	-0.620109764446

pre-reactive complex, CPCM/BLYP/6-311++G(d,p)

C	1.044148934950	-1.010344870029	-0.436341719177
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C	-0.360044657655	-1.414712890315	0.058945369291
H	1.124347907832	-1.088520644473	-1.525812343273
Cl	-0.790380412519	-3.091334244864	-0.612896325601
Cl	2.294299130230	-2.215916025675	0.212148761249
H	-0.362484300008	-1.468147101600	1.157959556524
O	0.180412035642	-0.171245990321	2.718094831556
H	-0.277438430882	0.376221754184	3.382147733497
C	-1.064194544420	1.026934889749	0.058430320904
H	-1.123095214384	1.083743510293	1.151612475750
C	0.349182179826	1.435286192171	-0.405187415806
H	0.382440613123	1.583657518536	-1.489658104453
C	1.401572637293	0.406901215790	0.056763416649
H	1.455937440061	0.408541816567	1.157081110972
C	-1.424934102853	-0.399575695878	-0.404645144354
H	-1.572229566734	-0.439540501546	-1.488623367823
Cl	-3.070548505512	-0.869250256312	0.311618412810
Cl	-2.301706728376	2.223653657081	-0.641222325808
Cl	0.763368691040	3.094920307549	0.311883714455
Cl	3.060975893345	0.896172359094	-0.619434957362

pre-reactive complex, gas-phase/B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)

C	1.3992211795	-0.3547714724	-0.3573688619
C	0.3805867362	-1.3967088172	0.1172880502
H	1.5103810096	-0.3884491940	-1.4423255515
Cl	0.8466238943	-3.0317871513	-0.5710132270
Cl	3.0533396801	-0.7716911452	0.2870622735
H	0.3820838038	-1.4296187887	1.2173266069
O	-0.0377085176	0.0205226506	2.4821345918
H	-0.0399331254	0.0440700844	3.4429415929
C	-1.4289511432	0.3662009034	0.0884433548
H	-1.4781337433	0.3842066449	1.1877736955
C	-0.4061481911	1.4034819053	-0.3869595526
H	-0.4250371866	1.4957296658	-1.4740090747
C	1.0025877312	1.0517056307	0.1040904239
H	1.0220087575	1.0902599755	1.2038110542
C	-1.0263608918	-1.0382884803	-0.3741068270
H	-1.0892458965	-1.1207238733	-1.4603139503
Cl	-2.2266127717	-2.2609979638	0.2502616444
Cl	-3.0646472300	0.7781647369	-0.6325820855
Cl	-0.8759673845	3.0566913442	0.2226741515
Cl	2.1903252896	2.2597143445	-0.6004173091

pre-reactive complex, IEFPCM/B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)

C	-1.411631988089	-0.363157638910	-0.417308140806
C	-1.016566994476	1.041424209099	0.052229358701
H	-1.533121638059	-0.397329666577	-1.498995297678
Cl	-2.209738058941	2.255762703793	-0.605148119035
Cl	-3.053067307739	-0.783404248249	0.260696329896
H	-1.048046864631	1.077303036635	1.144647294689
O	0.016382527476	0.018783337836	2.666594595081
H	-0.045198016380	-0.016992406325	3.627531387594
C	1.410777091403	0.364237575002	0.054067614842
H	1.452406997790	0.375303682597	1.146539755475
C	1.023199329024	-1.040211529240	-0.422927959931
H	1.104329816182	-1.125543732759	-1.505756234520
C	-0.387216300696	-1.398802563158	0.058636785794
H	-0.394255284632	-1.436202920071	1.151560702196

C	0.393675209409	1.405812404817	-0.425228515338
H	0.426209586325	1.517404766828	-1.508172929715
C1	0.849328949955	3.044132341737	0.236561506132
C1	3.062204928023	0.790491303164	-0.594278865760
C1	2.212688758897	-2.253280666087	0.242780653079
C1	-0.848246740882	-3.043048990074	-0.584804920695

pre-reactive complex, CPCM/B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)

C	1.4118083413	-0.3692089531	-0.4161810943
C	0.3839335608	-1.4036149319	0.0545862013
H	1.5331579864	-0.3979180180	-1.4981605968
C1	0.8366110413	-3.0464784519	-0.5971006787
C1	3.0517946144	-0.8002269284	0.2587520081
H	0.3922733325	-1.4482119016	1.1473103611
O	-0.0007254402	-0.0148719101	2.6684177412
H	-0.0413197213	-0.0113001032	3.6313629093
C	-1.4086339617	0.3676435937	0.0515387474
H	-1.4536013342	0.3753855731	1.1443705973
C	-0.3863031218	1.4083691702	-0.4175260991
H	-0.4153327404	1.5308581692	-1.4994943000
C	1.0204390111	1.0337048157	0.0626379469
H	1.0459974718	1.0608101456	1.1558185701
C	-1.0247343017	-1.0375092161	-0.4255975702
H	-1.1064077435	-1.1227115973	-1.5082374696
C1	-2.2204553680	-2.2456428478	0.2394453723
C1	-3.0555414405	0.8009583021	-0.6036611974
C1	-0.8378057682	3.0423166866	0.2591528586
C1	2.2219415818	2.2486384032	-0.5772953075

pre-reactive complex, gas-phase/M06-2X/6-311++G(d,p)

C	1.3924140648	-0.3519643450	-0.3510459774
C	0.3808439614	-1.3937520825	0.1219964919
H	1.4907012149	-0.3826574218	-1.4392536703
C1	0.8368152532	-2.9992163072	-0.5758661741
C1	3.0214993027	-0.7625982663	0.2903725782
H	0.3853865775	-1.4314610920	1.2201595210
O	-0.0370819617	0.0253062833	2.4547770314
H	-0.0448616929	0.0303773432	3.4128895485
C	-1.4266612670	0.3661398585	0.0934982895
H	-1.4826936578	0.3872301682	1.1906422464
C	-0.4041268825	1.3969012541	-0.3804707164
H	-0.4195114985	1.4749273955	-1.4707725566
C	1.0010278587	1.0510625251	0.1082534668
H	1.0249700849	1.0937951662	1.2060118442
C	-1.0210043367	-1.0332012553	-0.3652627395
H	-1.0770823079	-1.1076512835	-1.4544436024
C1	-2.2029070451	-2.2367011125	0.2598911640
C1	-3.0312954026	0.7697323400	-0.6373496818
C1	-0.8659642849	3.0259111951	0.2249786669
C1	2.1679440193	2.2355306371	-0.6042947305

pre-reactive complex, IEFPCM/M06-2X/6-311++G(d,p)

C	-1.4047330284	-0.3611524332	-0.4169960319
C	-1.0147123528	1.0355716735	0.0603867757
H	-1.5049787386	-0.3894373080	-1.5035600335
C1	-2.1900486832	2.2343279109	-0.5915941204
C1	-3.0271082373	-0.7759451876	0.2429381682

H	-1.0411919488	1.0622220091	1.1540286398
O	-0.0095435752	0.0000618729	2.6142712416
H	0.0125484801	0.0347429863	3.5743600506
C	1.4037462246	0.3610679886	0.0629008615
H	1.4390459157	0.3721888611	1.1561367589
C	1.0157575433	-1.0372252328	-0.4118043958
H	1.0922936503	-1.1165769640	-1.4977953568
C	-0.3898064374	-1.3950977474	0.0655000692
H	-0.4009884824	-1.4284867560	1.1589816662
C	0.3899452967	1.3970665912	-0.4173454395
H	0.4183178509	1.4980437527	-1.5037292324
C1	0.8399743399	3.0101940148	0.2433282341
C1	3.0304320485	0.7769611552	-0.5874399844
C1	2.1851113101	-2.2307930561	0.2572222250
C1	-0.8399471760	-3.0150531314	-0.5805651159

pre-reactive complex, CPCM/M06-2X/6-311++G(d,p)

C	-1.039401598716	-1.014849444074	-0.414248610878
C	-1.396009677224	0.391193521790	0.062451724104
H	-1.117566588458	-1.091879127218	-1.500275588832
C1	-3.013510367560	0.844469859102	-0.586865880881
C1	-2.236151408789	-2.182655089297	0.253695629816
H	-1.431760242490	0.401684294117	1.155818505032
O	0.009012200307	0.015881332023	2.614774195200
H	0.006488943556	-0.008004825317	3.575403801975
C	1.036453484291	1.011044264402	0.061840007199
H	1.060579556029	1.033181633398	1.155697526554
C	1.396440993851	-0.393053194071	-0.417936689328
H	1.498255651623	-0.422565436661	-1.504365595921
C	0.357912574256	-1.404136894631	0.063263850535
H	0.367682993515	-1.435137905196	1.156901875125
C	-0.359177092014	1.405168255791	-0.416271809388
H	-0.385702444282	1.508957668342	-1.502491934774
C1	-0.773206297097	3.026442155768	0.248569332457
C1	2.238791962177	2.185554460785	-0.584544999357
C1	3.008396186154	-0.844875628370	0.245012409309
C1	0.773068170871	-3.033853900685	-0.581178747946

TS, gas-phase/HF/6-311++G(d,p)

C	0.7855498850	-1.1836721734	-0.3820086866
C	-0.6480072884	-1.2130149364	0.1394686851
H	0.8550197430	-1.2833412379	-1.4589055298
C1	-1.4270242362	-2.7494044095	-0.4688864177
C1	1.7209557186	-2.5906189284	0.2618284800
H	-0.5927233541	-1.0236719644	1.4533875586
O	-0.3373007891	-0.4648131032	2.5539525642
H	-0.6173403421	-0.9563784576	3.3047818253
C	-0.7835188289	1.2779230496	0.0042414159
H	-0.9111705451	1.3863543972	1.0681855559
C	0.6980952880	1.3427583177	-0.3718380074
H	0.7983679445	1.4681676484	-1.4392171962
C	1.4743941794	0.1036119645	0.0783824470
H	1.5814395683	0.0901340557	1.1500067649
C	-1.4181678986	-0.0374899450	-0.4545611779
H	-1.4836463966	-0.0668009868	-1.5359136944
C1	-3.1383030207	-0.0633192462	0.1017779268
C1	-1.6218407570	2.6756990619	-0.7871537066

C1	1.4402836114	2.8156696128	0.3553607561
C1	3.1388285185	0.1995752810	-0.6310965634

TS, IEFPCM/HF/6-311++G(d,p)

C	-0.6520980226	-1.2071132161	-0.3318978651
C	-1.3144148788	0.0712978383	0.168276087
H	-0.7465042173	-1.3556093272	-1.3985375168
C1	-3.0246032825	0.0828555839	-0.5227486413
C1	-1.4796217635	-2.6482200249	0.4015876462
H	-1.3977726203	0.1082268862	1.5354279143
O	-1.4209770561	0.1618093260	2.7598638379
H	-1.6110937456	-0.6981607784	3.0957063281
C	0.8742197971	1.2889956935	-0.0011445189
H	0.9588002190	1.4420994262	1.0620216683
C	1.5754506828	-0.0075090180	-0.4119311133
H	1.6916335373	-0.0420888464	-1.4835172543
C	0.8219371638	-1.2465015244	0.0771201441
H	0.9054854724	-1.3381538521	1.1474949145
C	-0.5987487752	1.2837129853	-0.4156321889
H	-0.6817986548	1.3585467795	-1.4910210111
C1	-1.3681957003	2.8054428234	0.2061258844
C1	1.7289422503	2.6747814234	-0.7772685578
C1	3.2438081579	-0.0218642994	0.2670498098
C1	1.6137484362	-2.7118828787	-0.6148255672

TS, CPCM/HF/6-311++G(d,p)

C	-0.6032375499	-1.2820673644	-0.4145551781
C	-1.3149326281	-0.0664139875	0.1674723971
H	-0.6866193179	-1.3583211293	-1.4897622222
C1	-3.0249848429	-0.0734003767	-0.5242448841
C1	-1.3777952166	-2.8005962943	0.2095308188
H	-1.3991800844	-0.1002594238	1.5350787303
O	-1.4283216878	-0.1590020243	2.7584601965
H	-1.5980260044	0.7033173908	3.0992037921
C	0.8256376537	1.2439442802	0.0760334827
H	0.9085615424	1.3361740486	1.1464122643
C	1.5754698438	0.0020669190	-0.4114644097
H	1.6929025460	0.0355989580	-1.4829112847
C	0.8697767748	-1.2919443096	-0.0002870795
H	0.9542673721	-1.4451670397	1.0628709835
C	-0.6482230930	1.2091851550	-0.3340576697
H	-0.7416543636	1.3572643863	-1.4008003794
C1	-1.4713203858	2.653722040 7	0.3981380426
C1	1.6229045420	2.7061930002	-0.6161508154
C1	3.2432787567	0.0113050072	0.2692366701
C1	1.7196931429	-2.6809342363	-0.7760534550

TS, gas-phase/BLYP/6-311++G(d,p)

C	0.8520672203	-1.1599248942	-0.4024636573
C	-0.5950690638	-1.2791074457	0.0687027963
H	0.9812071700	-1.2576997061	-1.4891089462
C1	-1.3181176468	-2.8402275529	-0.6832445897
C1	1.8700267031	-2.5950416984	0.2555697987
H	-0.5544744828	-1.1739170903	1.3777158114
O	-0.2649954060	-0.6184265102	2.5534354756
H	-1.1038940157	-0.5766326916	3.0460544651
C	-0.8322860899	1.2374305774	0.0428741658

H	-0.9473314938	1.3304347494	1.1273470268
C	0.6519381976	1.3729277735	-0.3492835555
H	0.7530382986	1.5192091169	-1.4306083731
C	1.4792672777	0.1554031431	0.1087082153
H	1.5638975643	0.1287672636	1.1994977574
C	-1.4283949561	-0.1057807668	-0.4247331445
H	-1.6160548698	-0.1028642239	-1.5061983748
C1	-3.1836716458	-0.2236129775	0.2798353107
C1	-1.7778657555	2.6459102891	-0.7332266966
C1	1.3492987638	2.9253014084	0.3937736224
C1	3.2050022307	0.3364872361	-0.5643441079

TS, IEFPCM/BLYP/6-311++G(d,p)

C	0.2596310794	-1.3900726048	-0.3770645700
C	-1.0528517983	-0.8009255029	0.1048429753
H	0.2876525281	-1.6210820301	-1.4481339931
C1	-2.4409548093	-1.8148146671	-0.6665822102
C1	0.5095140108	-3.1105749344	0.3955117349
H	-1.1657248160	-0.8831118501	1.4557359242
O	-1.2062919469	-0.9168096891	2.7358847476
H	-1.8083752143	-0.1865468662	2.9676217394
C	-0.0470339467	1.5296583488	0.0448623947
H	-0.0214188325	1.6811038222	1.1279843617
C	1.2893320411	0.9393261890	-0.4512296405
H	1.3600904353	1.0020249338	-1.5419606233
C	1.4676745275	-0.5183655777	0.0229789023
H	1.6276269632	-0.5556076263	1.1044068031
C	-1.2394915578	0.6346704333	-0.3480661754
H	-1.4793465321	0.7496894124	-1.4110651991
C1	-2.7961419483	1.3634688899	0.4791374435
C1	-0.2669173505	3.2193316043	-0.6794407394
C1	2.6899361297	1.9705086321	0.1846673205
C1	3.0146030375	-1.2083639169	-0.7241421963

TS, CPCM/BLYP/6-311++G(d,p)

C	0.2613908968	-1.3900487442	-0.3778122819
C	-1.0527033724	-0.8039520019	0.1027265479
H	0.2912989531	-1.6216795472	-1.4486610972
C1	-2.4381318118	-1.8215877933	-0.6689600152
C1	0.5143379071	-3.1100712262	0.3960598018
H	-1.1637912329	-0.8850172456	1.4550426462
O	-1.1991584294	-0.9189839699	2.7337485242
H	-1.7848454386	-0.1769177283	2.9700224992
C	-0.0525587458	1.5286679940	0.0445007437
H	-0.0286951758	1.6795910425	1.1277417470
C	1.2859414628	0.9417294047	-0.4499190543
H	1.3585270797	1.0052841704	-1.5404317483
C	1.4669252614	-0.5157019964	0.0239865721
H	1.6251858198	-0.5529269674	1.1056916985
C	-1.2424967401	0.6310661940	-0.3501205271
H	-1.4820880422	0.7461260516	-1.4131369521
C1	-2.8017389831	1.3559219612	0.4766630588
C1	-0.2755142464	3.2181866921	-0.6791954418
C1	2.6831483359	1.9759032946	0.1890259296
C1	3.0164785018	-1.2020825848	-0.7210236511

TS, gas-phase/B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)

C	0.7916867731	-1.1807997037	-0.3735407905
C	-0.6468908092	-1.2314244926	0.1154931039
H	0.8992817862	-1.2969967419	-1.4562803475
Cl	-1.4089036011	-2.7841421323	-0.5175486087
Cl	1.7475702013	-2.6012455638	0.3028797973
H	-0.5903572897	-1.0245415204	1.4286283502
O	-0.3053996112	-0.3828424220	2.5128831055
H	-0.5833073564	-0.8881561700	3.2823348515
C	-0.8071307696	1.2623515145	0.0188748239
H	-0.9304076029	1.3479698057	1.0981197517
C	0.6738547143	1.3456094442	-0.3639792155
H	0.7755968539	1.4690917316	-1.4422457484
C	1.4599616065	0.1159215619	0.1015704012
H	1.5392093217	0.0994236127	1.1881975837
C	-1.4277212156	-0.0583213095	-0.4549708341
H	-1.5212372539	-0.0723820659	-1.5451412457
Cl	-3.1750967641	-0.1119465143	0.1216871945
Cl	-1.6810238529	2.6760360000	-0.752834115
Cl	1.4113298720	2.8554483990	0.3518576112
Cl	3.1585129974	0.2284565668	-0.5767376693

TS, IEFPCM/B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)

C	0.6159263419	1.2844834552	-0.4085256011
C	1.3193046564	0.0634776246	0.1482842303
H	0.7209873708	1.4081219077	-1.4881054230
Cl	3.0383871030	0.0539442351	-0.5524804872
Cl	1.4022954060	2.8193330979	0.2683054811
H	1.3973989929	0.1003927126	1.5192284722
O	1.3990994550	0.1475215195	2.7640051532
H	1.4929573162	-0.7665677587	3.0553017990
C	-0.8378213798	-1.2318462623	0.0743520001
H	-0.9431712129	-1.3078747606	1.1546162480
C	-1.5692564252	0.0091836626	-0.4475616298
H	-1.6566801080	-0.0286826080	-1.5323832025
C	-0.8652769222	1.2995820237	-0.0150154416
H	-0.9678669842	1.4487452945	1.0577381068
C	0.6450223417	-1.2131861730	-0.3115886193
H	0.7629726129	-1.4245185525	-1.3758855096
Cl	1.4595815275	-2.6701482409	0.4983767872
Cl	-1.6395310006	-2.7224687731	-0.6081522346
Cl	-3.2815649682	0.0110925062	0.1804692860
Cl	-1.7043041230	2.7194690896	-0.7960664151

TS, CPCM/B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)

C	0.6150153693	1.2865541853	-0.4078277500
C	1.3206047957	0.0660394345	0.1467768523
H	0.7206835963	1.4130584783	-1.4869444543
Cl	3.0391041301	0.0598673970	-0.5560618038
Cl	1.3981331121	2.8221425449	0.2731301353
H	1.3992671276	0.1006441864	1.5186333113
O	1.4018107778	0.1448221316	2.7624627772
H	1.4713877207	-0.7720592759	3.0517663783
C	-0.8344529799	-1.2325052128	0.0750397215
H	-0.9386098075	-1.3080313616	1.1554691003
C	-1.5684064625	0.0070678815	-0.4467886707
H	-1.6568122481	-0.0313779620	-1.5314788394

C	-0.8663833955	1.2988425774	-0.0150040090
H	-0.9696538489	1.4485824536	1.0575942092
C	0.6479268183	-1.2115546294	-0.3126110250
H	0.7652517131	-1.4231943701	-1.3768682642
C1	1.4656923727	-2.6673626572	0.4970241138
C1	-1.6344091684	-2.7249651789	-0.6054346029
C1	-3.2801805801	0.0064238475	0.1829628224
C1	-1.7075090428	2.7170595299	-0.7969270022

TS, gas-phase/M06-2X/6-311++G(d,p)

C	-0.702867315552	-1.235641728086	-0.422993174512
C	-1.409629787949	0.009765127753	0.085634081183
H	-0.714699773866	-1.329340564745	-1.514715540860
C1	-3.090849517792	0.019735014354	-0.586875458515
C1	-1.555912305511	-2.714539773087	0.173473753810
H	-1.229919190323	0.009576954171	1.369581777344
O	-0.480369910254	0.010045232341	2.461220060143
H	-0.989987909488	-0.048183007396	3.271087049991
C	0.749584071388	1.258851506136	0.102125124738
H	0.732281240864	1.345150207044	1.190516099764
C	1.488163822753	-0.008750422129	-0.320550908358
H	1.642154288598	-0.008287581805	-1.401896396595
C	0.733906105552	-1.267888751685	0.099491466045
H	0.717473251743	-1.355019159593	1.187673779350
C	-0.686034000233	1.244910311073	-0.424749139658
H	-0.692358521258	1.334739210792	-1.516909990675
C1	-1.522312031502	2.736136669741	0.162887549804
C1	1.632247842555	2.683782859574	-0.573159515036
C1	3.135853769922	-0.020285618894	0.405370193904
C1	1.596996870346	-2.702678485504	-0.580207811868

TS, IEFPCM/M06-2X/6-311++G(d,p)

C	0.2439725576	1.3838474730	-0.4301039122
C	1.2621406463	0.3326695125	-0.2656453331
H	0.1074677180	1.7627705221	-1.4469578380
C1	2.6881407295	0.7153008763	-1.3207717417
C1	0.7950831415	2.9706122364	0.4417669896
H	1.8941564378	0.4021323879	1.5181231072
O	2.2271873658	0.3474997799	2.4562298653
H	2.5007188706	-0.5711204891	2.5364997311
C	-0.5028400528	-1.3990951957	0.1123762518
H	-0.4309262485	-1.4478746788	1.1990193145
C	-1.5500579867	-0.3661098999	-0.2922261549
H	-1.7086117797	-0.3747623987	-1.3715270153
C	-1.1050436038	1.0146706636	0.1800232142
H	-1.0495839000	1.0347160044	1.2684815183
C	0.8533648006	-1.0583118030	-0.4967794363
H	0.9124293682	-1.4172112356	-1.5276374303
C1	2.0966820482	-2.2589775122	0.3174557599
C1	-1.0161011667	-3.0367659695	-0.4291686393
C1	-3.1311535139	-0.7816806091	0.4609454310
C1	-2.3342204319	2.2446773355	-0.2822226820

TS, CPCM/M06-2X/6-311++G(d,p)

C	0.2441035883	1.3842634629	-0.4307003214
C	1.2624572293	0.3334034238	-0.2687033935
H	0.1072188274	1.7647872764	-1.4468158293

C1	2.6864165750	0.7162654755	-1.3264614793
C1	0.7957167557	2.9713191618	0.4426236650
H	1.8937045545	0.4007551550	1.5181890191
O	2.2253567332	0.3454330260	2.4564405438
H	2.4912728981	-0.5752050090	2.5392800502
C	-0.5013404560	-1.3985090705	0.1133357401
H	-0.4285128541	-1.4459232613	1.1999866695
C	-1.5492541968	-0.3662999048	-0.2917019464
H	-1.7080063560	-0.3756661187	-1.3709469986
C	-1.1045655580	1.0148003496	0.1799001888
H	-1.0489508305	1.0351615877	1.2683378852
C	0.8540558796	-1.0577370373	-0.4975976639
H	0.9124082956	-1.4179644060	-1.5279700199
C1	2.0991300476	-2.2579697360	0.3165730449
C1	-1.0145449024	-3.0369915844	-0.4256828415
C1	-3.1300073800	-0.7816915669	0.4620556817
C1	-2.3338538504	2.2447557762	-0.2822609945

Table S6. Cartesian coordinates of all structures at CPCM(water)/M06-2X/6-311++G(d,p) level. **β -HCH (all-equatorial conformer)**

C	0.000000	1.455793	0.2334200
C	-1.260754	-0.727897	0.2334200
C	1.260754	-0.727897	0.2334200
C	0.000000	-1.455793	-0.2334200
C	1.260754	0.727897	-0.2334200
C	-1.260754	0.727897	-0.2334200
H	0.000000	-1.551579	-1.3201300
H	1.343707	0.775790	-1.3201300
H	-1.343707	0.775790	-1.3201300
H	0.000000	1.551579	1.3201300
H	-1.343707	-0.775790	1.3201300
H	1.343707	-0.775790	1.3201300
Cl	0.000000	3.123161	-0.4266540
Cl	2.704737	-1.561581	-0.4266540
Cl	-2.704737	-1.561581	-0.4266540
Cl	0.000000	-3.123161	0.4266540
Cl	-2.704737	1.561581	0.4266540
Cl	2.704737	1.561581	0.4266540

 β -HCH (all-axial conformer)

C	0.157403	1.064736	-1.0574670
C	-0.155593	-0.383859	-1.4504750
C	0.157871	-1.448413	-0.3929020
C	-0.157404	-1.064737	1.0574660
C	0.155592	0.383858	1.4504750
C	-0.157870	1.448413	0.3929010
H	-0.382959	-2.357859	-0.6398510
H	0.384367	-0.624913	-2.3620060
H	-0.382810	1.732919	-1.7224600
H	0.382809	-1.732920	1.7224590
H	-0.384370	0.624912	2.3620050
H	0.382963	2.357858	0.6398490
Cl	-1.897939	-1.411258	1.3973100
Cl	1.898381	-1.918698	-0.5192760
Cl	-1.896617	-0.508511	-1.9186690
Cl	1.897939	1.411256	-1.3973140
Cl	-1.898378	1.918702	0.5192750
Cl	1.896615	0.508510	1.9186740

hydroxide anion (HO⁻)

O	0.000000	0.000000	0.1067680
H	0.000000	0.000000	-0.8541430

water (H₂O)

O	0.000000	0.000000	0.1177760
H	0.000000	0.759695	-0.4711050
H	0.000000	-0.759695	-0.4711050

chloride anion (Cl⁻)

Cl	0.000000	0.000000	0.0000000
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pre-reactive complex β -HCH $\rightarrow$ 1: 1,2

C	-1.404625591021	-0.362252253032	-0.416307657260
C	-1.013885431539	1.034859764816	0.059791763513

H	-1.509031489533	-0.390541905105	-1.502449351314
C1	-2.189899894783	2.232677552150	-0.591564919840
C1	-3.023967146452	-0.777996538628	0.251212232338
H	-1.041347776822	1.061641070019	1.152935267833
O	-0.012973814700	-0.001630795948	2.612299712436
H	0.008580060207	0.032928786210	3.572303564510
C	1.404082061022	0.361452517892	0.061724851031
H	1.437649132712	0.370158985779	1.155138319574
C	1.016159131633	-1.036298199597	-0.414776809422
H	1.090670095597	-1.116204189407	-1.500622139632
C	-0.388616348986	-1.395614944224	0.063323622828
H	-0.399810170094	-1.430382432497	1.156603051309
C	0.390918911997	1.399252682232	-0.415706297461
H	0.422272988512	1.507064831475	-1.501480427292
C1	0.838232084685	3.009445711059	0.256012162520
C1	3.031236487964	0.778661586141	-0.586938583967
C1	2.187553291733	-2.229411138756	0.252405359118
C1	-0.839082582178	-3.015130090564	-0.584678720821

TS β -HCH $\rightarrow$ 1: 1,2

C	0.2441035883	1.3842634629	-0.4307003214
C	1.2624572293	0.3334034238	-0.2687033935
H	0.1072188274	1.7647872764	-1.4468158293
C1	2.6864165750	0.7162654755	-1.3264614793
C1	0.7957167557	2.9713191618	0.4426236650
H	1.8937045545	0.4007551550	1.5181890191
O	2.2253567332	0.3454330260	2.4564405438
H	2.4912728981	-0.5752050090	2.5392800502
C	-0.5013404560	-1.3985090705	0.1133357401
H	-0.4285128541	-1.4459232613	1.1999866695
C	-1.5492541968	-0.3662999048	-0.2917019464
H	-1.7080063560	-0.3756661187	-1.3709469986
C	-1.1045655580	1.0148003496	0.1799001888
H	-1.0489508305	1.0351615877	1.2683378852
C	0.8540558796	-1.0577370373	-0.4975976639
H	0.9124082956	-1.4179644060	-1.5279700199
C1	2.0991300476	-2.2579697360	0.3165730449
C1	-1.0145449024	-3.0369915844	-0.4256828415
C1	-3.1300073800	-0.7816915669	0.4620556817
C1	-2.3338538504	2.2447557762	-0.2822609945

post-reactive complex β -HCH $\rightarrow$ 1: 1,2

C	-0.1981351243	-1.5539456349	-0.7731828480
C	-1.05367444745	-0.3746172493	-1.1335528666
H	0.1624888123	-2.0419887448	-1.6797571279
C1	-2.5252735288	-0.7432197324	-1.9894926258
C1	-1.1718404516	-2.8166685153	0.0817985319
H	-1.8708043409	-0.7556231575	1.8946347381
O	-1.1934011406	-0.1645238405	2.2376299194
H	-1.5247952782	0.7341389055	2.0513425211
C	0.5440346028	1.2668089214	-0.2032387985
H	0.3476378159	1.5325178832	0.8362610225
C	1.5920657545	0.1637170477	-0.3025677121
H	1.9805366182	0.0937520473	-1.3193927527
C	0.9689464876	-1.1586602272	0.1363305949
H	0.6157214898	-1.0674919358	1.1631280859
C	-0.7304211079	0.8878317307	-0.8895004870
H	-1.3959315726	1.6941088161	-1.1695976830
C1	-2.0433578273	2.8122032356	1.5972276741

C1	1.1799008902	2.7756902392	-0.9677602463
C1	2.9861346435	0.5731760164	0.7520093861
C1	2.1799188521	-2.4849032254	0.1067704940

rel-(3R,4S,5R,6S)-1,3,4,5,6-pentachlorocyclohex-1-ene (1)

C	-0.145741	-1.752222	0.3187690
C	-1.228770	-1.073163	-0.0359760
C	-1.254513	0.407786	-0.2892260
C	0.038225	1.082944	0.1786330
C	1.261633	0.252250	-0.2027190
C	1.191704	-1.102222	0.4963010
H	-0.198389	-2.822035	0.4787220
H	0.012477	1.227845	1.2591930
H	1.309489	0.117935	-1.2841060
H	1.442817	-1.000420	1.5530520
H	-1.428997	0.599524	-1.3488240
C1	-2.724399	-1.914037	-0.3179110
C1	2.455792	-2.195170	-0.1870510
C1	2.770347	1.090819	0.2803580
C1	0.119213	2.719336	-0.5497310
C1	-2.639342	1.180517	0.5712340

pre-reactive complex 1→2: 1,2 (C4) E2 path

C	0.176094	1.886169	-0.216300
C	-0.994394	1.216928	-0.178338
C	-1.170998	-0.200638	-0.180619
C	0.050612	-0.981268	-0.490288
C	1.316816	-0.306849	0.042355
C	1.441236	1.125928	-0.468364
H	0.233201	2.949527	-0.035489
H	0.170591	-1.239878	-1.545606
H	1.299483	-0.304747	1.132523
H	1.757035	1.135922	-1.513492
C1	-2.454118	2.190989	0.038066
C1	2.814452	1.939388	0.408117
C1	2.777693	-1.250968	-0.439811
C1	-0.049676	-2.671410	0.299802
C1	-2.563734	-0.812201	-1.146112
H	-1.615340	-0.563950	1.660488
O	-1.785381	-0.807859	2.605985
H	-1.396603	-1.684192	2.681959

TS 1→2: 1,2 (C4) E2 path

C	0.223375	-1.732425	-0.5586720
C	1.292590	-1.083254	-0.1172370
C	1.306985	0.385176	0.2003330
C	0.074255	1.083661	-0.3792270
C	-1.169182	0.279599	-0.0564960
C	-1.093011	-1.051395	-0.7651930
H	0.273547	-2.796081	-0.7575170
H	0.218758	1.269779	-1.4472610
H	-1.338060	-0.998853	-1.8290710
H	1.352702	0.531224	1.2802020
C1	2.761015	-1.961964	0.2177310
C1	-2.385464	-2.174948	-0.0991120
C1	-2.632839	1.155087	-0.6923110
C1	-0.019833	2.732731	0.3680160
C1	2.794004	1.170912	-0.4646280

H	-1.267759	0.120073	1.2567640
O	-1.264358	-0.028478	2.5311580
H	-1.721437	-0.857390	2.7017400

post-reactive complex: 1,2 (C4) E2 path

C	-0.620539	-1.081413	-1.2040890
C	0.497269	-1.356887	-0.5385900
C	1.311316	-0.320322	0.1736920
C	0.912568	1.139820	-0.1326510
C	-0.424348	1.304985	-0.7930790
C	-1.094107	0.292303	-1.3373630
H	-1.230403	-1.876424	-1.6114370
H	1.657322	1.594403	-0.7870120
H	-2.008153	0.471027	-1.8880870
H	1.216816	-0.510572	1.2410370
Cl	0.971010	-3.004146	-0.2426960
Cl	-3.650406	-1.308669	0.4161390
Cl	-0.955797	2.945901	-1.0192460
Cl	1.039891	2.100553	1.3986890
Cl	3.079983	-0.509534	-0.1838980
H	-1.193609	0.522669	2.2252080
O	-1.043863	-0.401811	2.0068950
H	-1.823613	-0.667316	1.4848420

pre-reactive complex 1→2: 1,2 (C4) E1cB

C	0.176094	1.886169	-0.216300
C	-0.994394	1.216928	-0.178338
C	-1.170998	-0.200638	-0.180619
C	0.050612	-0.981268	-0.490288
C	1.316816	-0.306849	0.042355
C	1.441236	1.125928	-0.468364
H	0.233201	2.949527	-0.035489
H	0.170591	-1.239878	-1.545606
H	1.299483	-0.304747	1.132523
H	1.757035	1.135922	-1.513492
Cl	-2.454118	2.190989	0.038066
Cl	2.814452	1.939388	0.408117
Cl	2.777693	-1.250968	-0.439811
Cl	-0.049676	-2.671410	0.299802
Cl	-2.563734	-0.812201	-1.146112
H	-1.615340	-0.563950	1.660488
O	-1.785381	-0.807859	2.605985
H	-1.396603	-1.684192	2.681959

TS 1→2: 1,2 (C4) E1cB path

C	0.249842	-1.764911	-0.5015010
C	1.307980	-1.078664	-0.0907770
C	1.296348	0.399675	0.1726200
C	0.040037	1.053846	-0.4083940
C	-1.182921	0.230234	-0.0531830
C	-1.080187	-1.116496	-0.7279170
H	0.320043	-2.834258	-0.6598060
H	0.167471	1.221765	-1.4813660
H	-1.319285	-1.091714	-1.7944250
H	1.359345	0.585056	1.2457590
Cl	2.795847	-1.913653	0.2705720

C1	-2.353341	-2.247658	-0.0454080
C1	-2.666042	1.060708	-0.7049770
C1	-0.084580	2.716241	0.3083610
C1	2.755798	1.191628	-0.5456470
H	-1.252382	0.159582	1.2731870
O	-1.221541	0.114610	2.5535370
H	-0.900036	0.977074	2.8339340

Reaction intermediate 1→2: 1,2 (C4) E1cB path

C	-0.287995	1.782203	-0.5011010
C	-1.334761	1.072853	-0.1014880
C	-1.281666	-0.402285	0.1709080
C	-0.021701	-1.031999	-0.4296080
C	1.190162	-0.198789	-0.1413040
C	1.055126	1.163988	-0.7136600
H	-0.379636	2.850784	-0.6537940
H	-0.195205	-1.278106	-1.4833160
H	1.364865	1.275316	-1.7569690
H	-1.323714	-0.580615	1.2461810
C1	-2.844090	1.874937	0.2515320
C1	2.281728	2.340955	0.1123460
C1	2.629641	-0.991555	-0.9567880
C1	0.148025	-2.696927	0.3455080
C1	-2.738765	-1.237691	-0.5060760
H	1.368155	-0.262793	1.6547450
O	1.383751	-0.371480	2.6627700
H	1.079360	-1.273799	2.7976430

Second TS 1→2: 1,2 (C4) E1cB path

C	-0.326390	1.780236	-0.5172810
C	-1.361223	1.059328	-0.1066980
C	-1.279071	-0.410229	0.1907260
C	-0.025795	-1.033538	-0.4292710
C	1.182141	-0.184944	-0.2062940
C	1.025019	1.183767	-0.7227490
H	-0.435036	2.845430	-0.6813570
H	-0.226120	-1.314833	-1.4689010
H	1.373192	1.357254	-1.7436050
H	-1.292420	-0.567875	1.2700000
C1	-2.881062	1.842191	0.2407930
C1	2.220422	2.385181	0.1860280
C1	2.601560	-0.957496	-1.0602980
C1	0.188803	-2.685587	0.3800310
C1	-2.738217	-1.282129	-0.4319640
H	1.493244	-0.270275	1.5952440
O	1.604942	-0.405673	2.5880690
H	1.303924	-1.308755	2.7254180

post-reactive complex 1→2: 1,2 (C4) E1cB path

C	-0.729204	-1.007744	-1.1928410
C	0.356578	-1.392151	-0.5284610
C	1.276565	-0.442033	0.1747120
C	1.018203	1.051850	-0.1227290
C	-0.293557	1.347652	-0.7881370
C	-1.061809	0.406360	-1.3297370
H	-1.418124	-1.738371	-1.5943940

H	1.806559	1.437142	-0.7705310
H	-1.951506	0.675307	-1.8837590
H	1.182614	-0.625930	1.2432580
Cl	0.663136	-3.078222	-0.2294950
Cl	-3.740133	-0.990472	0.3995070
Cl	-0.658018	3.033044	-1.0182600
Cl	1.228568	1.990354	1.4135640
Cl	3.014392	-0.801517	-0.2120430
H	-1.872714	-0.490385	1.4754310
O	-1.078755	-0.286766	2.0042140
H	-1.152496	0.648579	2.2138050

trans-1,4,5,6-tetrachlorocyclohexa-1,3-diene (2)

C	-0.750270	0.139526	-0.7551850
C	0.750270	-0.139521	-0.7551880
C	1.394293	0.212050	0.5469640
C	0.708844	0.174061	1.6911610
C	-0.708846	-0.174065	1.6911610
C	-1.394295	-0.212050	0.5469630
H	1.220475	0.379442	-1.5868570
H	-1.220479	-0.379427	-1.5868580
H	1.200663	0.381490	2.6327440
H	-1.200663	-0.381500	2.6327430
Cl	-3.086166	-0.564611	0.4906660
Cl	3.086167	0.564600	0.4906700
Cl	1.000492	-1.906660	-1.0755860
Cl	-1.000491	1.906671	-1.0755760

trans-1,3,4,6-tetrachlorocyclohexa-1,4-diene (3)

C	1.162923	0.679562	0.6209310
C	1.229540	-0.678166	0.0022740
C	0.199960	-1.285799	-0.5715610
C	-1.162924	-0.679562	-0.6209310
C	-1.229540	0.678165	-0.0022740
C	-0.199960	1.285799	0.5715600
H	1.551073	0.658672	1.6393690
H	-1.551076	-0.658674	-1.6393680
H	-0.308503	2.274420	1.0005550
H	0.308503	-2.274420	-1.0005570
Cl	2.778980	-1.463338	0.0913740
Cl	-2.778980	1.463339	-0.0913760
Cl	-2.300918	-1.805315	0.2611380
Cl	2.300919	1.805315	-0.2611350

trans-1,3,5,6-tetrachlorocyclohexa-1,4-diene (4)

C	0.992392	0.000002	-0.3434930
C	0.192436	1.240341	-0.1010670
C	-1.033676	1.255601	0.4034220
C	-1.759501	-0.000002	0.7486020
C	-1.033673	-1.255603	0.4034210
C	0.192439	-1.240340	-0.1010690
H	1.416918	0.000002	-1.3474160
H	-2.060831	-0.000003	1.7965920
H	-1.552864	-2.191941	0.5659760
H	-1.552870	2.191936	0.5659770
Cl	0.996357	2.723041	-0.5286190

C1	0.996366	-2.723038	-0.5286190
C1	-3.351022	-0.000004	-0.1544570
C1	2.443425	0.000002	0.7622810

pre-reactive complex 1→5: 1,2 (C5)

C	0.176094	1.886169	-0.216300
C	-0.994394	1.216928	-0.178338
C	-1.170998	-0.200638	-0.180619
C	0.050612	-0.981268	-0.490288
C	1.316816	-0.306849	0.042355
C	1.441236	1.125928	-0.468364
H	0.233201	2.949527	-0.035489
H	0.170591	-1.239878	-1.545606
H	1.299483	-0.304747	1.132523
H	1.757035	1.135922	-1.513492
C1	-2.454118	2.190989	0.038066
C1	2.814452	1.939388	0.408117
C1	2.777693	-1.250968	-0.439811
C1	-0.049676	-2.671410	0.299802
C1	-2.563734	-0.812201	-1.146112
H	-1.615340	-0.563950	1.660488
O	-1.785381	-0.807859	2.605985
H	-1.396603	-1.684192	2.681959

TS 1→5: 1,2 (C5)

C	0.158721	1.808297	0.2707020
C	1.234897	1.152745	-0.1439660
C	1.249239	-0.305657	-0.4935550
C	-0.040907	-0.993820	-0.0981750
C	-1.239081	-0.129975	-0.4433580
C	-1.169212	1.129753	0.4126320
H	0.211185	2.864212	0.5058610
H	-1.322992	0.131669	-1.5021550
H	-1.376317	0.880200	1.4539200
H	1.509910	-0.428059	-1.5477130
C1	2.732420	2.019296	-0.3790990
C1	-2.459772	2.300361	-0.0823070
C1	-2.777287	-1.002546	-0.0515450
C1	-0.116539	-2.553232	-1.0314960
C1	2.642408	-1.123063	0.3795610
H	-0.068044	-1.226824	1.2076500
O	-0.153059	-1.328290	2.4832020
H	0.747892	-1.456813	2.7942060

post-reactive complex 1→5: 1,2 (C5)

C	-0.086801	1.847261	0.1128360
C	0.939449	1.309119	-0.5393330
C	0.945334	-0.072199	-1.0210730
C	-0.163964	-0.800672	-0.9357420
C	-1.470853	-0.219725	-0.4508170
C	-1.272244	0.997871	0.4590850
H	-0.057105	2.858381	0.4974720
H	-2.062674	0.051210	-1.3286070
H	-1.174234	0.662765	1.4915630
H	1.853533	-0.475185	-1.4462890
C1	2.375850	2.238407	-0.8657140
C1	-2.780454	1.999425	0.4185570
C1	-2.481673	-1.424845	0.4298490

C1	-0.200050	-2.409558	-1.5839280
C1	3.333967	-1.053348	1.2078790
H	-0.063137	-1.785893	1.9602780
O	0.338082	-0.956387	2.2361710
H	1.243563	-0.981484	1.8735710

pre-reactive complex 1→5: 1,4 (C3)

C	0.176094	1.886169	-0.216300
C	-0.994394	1.216928	-0.178338
C	-1.170998	-0.200638	-0.180619
C	0.050612	-0.981268	-0.490288
C	1.316816	-0.306849	0.042355
C	1.441236	1.125928	-0.468364
H	0.233201	2.949527	-0.035489
H	0.170591	-1.239878	-1.545606
H	1.299483	-0.304747	1.132523
H	1.757035	1.135922	-1.513492
C1	-2.454118	2.190989	0.038066
C1	2.814452	1.939388	0.408117
C1	2.777693	-1.250968	-0.439811
C1	-0.049676	-2.671410	0.299802
C1	-2.563734	-0.812201	-1.146112
H	-1.615340	-0.563950	1.660488
O	-1.785381	-0.807859	2.605985
H	-1.396603	-1.684192	2.681959

TS 1→5: 1,4 (C3)

C	-0.200649	-1.719880	-0.1369290
C	-1.364829	-1.024706	-0.3568020
C	-1.426797	0.415433	-0.3997950
C	-0.060638	1.082460	-0.1753480
C	1.147070	0.252228	-0.6202130
C	1.051843	-1.113494	-0.0230590
H	-0.253618	-2.803257	-0.0860690
H	0.059233	1.280364	0.8886660
H	1.241396	0.238477	-1.7125380
H	-1.988239	0.837305	-1.2285270
C1	-2.888790	-1.883951	-0.5258110
C1	2.451910	-2.158513	-0.3869920
C1	2.648101	1.128077	-0.0576230
C1	-0.064779	2.697128	-0.9749880
C1	-2.534793	1.125359	1.0582760
H	1.148529	-0.661940	1.9541720
O	1.200077	-0.257414	2.8460550
H	1.918044	0.378419	2.7700730

post-reactive complex 1→5: 1,4 (C3)

C	-0.853151	1.781563	0.0018450
C	0.551555	1.706375	-0.4037140
C	1.160990	0.563236	-0.7013760
C	0.419011	-0.729070	-0.5393450
C	-1.101448	-0.598950	-0.6609200
C	-1.617133	0.692989	-0.0690490
H	-1.258608	2.729683	0.3300910
H	0.688672	-1.158314	0.4271280
H	-1.404792	-0.625639	-1.7107770
H	2.215972	0.508881	-0.9321320
C1	1.416020	3.220374	-0.4463550

C1	-3.305831	0.782500	0.3088820
C1	-1.861532	-2.057157	0.0755190
C1	0.994789	-1.925513	-1.7676730
C1	3.503877	-1.039152	1.2408390
H	-0.599207	0.408730	2.7264930
O	-0.320606	-0.504997	2.6123570
H	-1.140600	-0.998082	2.5050850

pre-reactive complex **1**→**5**: 1,2 (C5)

C	0.176094	1.886169	-0.216300
C	-0.994394	1.216928	-0.178338
C	-1.170998	-0.200638	-0.180619
C	0.050612	-0.981268	-0.490288
C	1.316816	-0.306849	0.042355
C	1.441236	1.125928	-0.468364
H	0.233201	2.949527	-0.035489
H	0.170591	-1.239878	-1.545606
H	1.299483	-0.304747	1.132523
H	1.757035	1.135922	-1.513492
C1	-2.454118	2.190989	0.038066
C1	2.814452	1.939388	0.408117
C1	2.777693	-1.250968	-0.439811
C1	-0.049676	-2.671410	0.299802
C1	-2.563734	-0.812201	-1.146112
H	-1.615340	-0.563950	1.660488
O	-1.785381	-0.807859	2.605985
H	-1.396603	-1.684192	2.681959

TS **1**→**5**: 1,2 (C5)

C	0.158721	1.808297	0.2707020
C	1.234897	1.152745	-0.1439660
C	1.249239	-0.305657	-0.4935550
C	-0.040907	-0.993820	-0.0981750
C	-1.239081	-0.129975	-0.4433580
C	-1.169212	1.129753	0.4126320
H	0.211185	2.864212	0.5058610
H	-1.322992	0.131669	-1.5021550
H	-1.376317	0.880200	1.4539200
H	1.509910	-0.428059	-1.5477130
C1	2.732420	2.019296	-0.3790990
C1	-2.459772	2.300361	-0.0823070
C1	-2.777287	-1.002546	-0.0515450
C1	-0.116539	-2.553232	-1.0314960
C1	2.642408	-1.123063	0.3795610
H	-0.068044	-1.226824	1.2076500
O	-0.153059	-1.328290	2.4832020
H	0.747892	-1.456813	2.7942060

post-reactive complex **1**→**5**: 1,2 (C5)

C	-0.086801	1.847261	0.1128360
C	0.939449	1.309119	-0.5393330
C	0.945334	-0.072199	-1.0210730
C	-0.163964	-0.800672	-0.9357420
C	-1.470853	-0.219725	-0.4508170
C	-1.272244	0.997871	0.4590850
H	-0.057105	2.858381	0.4974720
H	-2.062674	0.051210	-1.3286070
H	-1.174234	0.662765	1.4915630

H	1.853533	-0.475185	-1.4462890
C1	2.375850	2.238407	-0.8657140
C1	-2.780454	1.999425	0.4185570
C1	-2.481673	-1.424845	0.4298490
C1	-0.200050	-2.409558	-1.5839280
C1	3.333967	-1.053348	1.2078790
H	-0.063137	-1.785893	1.9602780
O	0.338082	-0.956387	2.2361710
H	1.243563	-0.981484	1.8735710

pre-reactive complex 1→5: 1,2 (C3)

C	0.176094	1.886169	-0.216300
C	-0.994394	1.216928	-0.178338
C	-1.170998	-0.200638	-0.180619
C	0.050612	-0.981268	-0.490288
C	1.316816	-0.306849	0.042355
C	1.441236	1.125928	-0.468364
H	0.233201	2.949527	-0.035489
H	0.170591	-1.239878	-1.545606
H	1.299483	-0.304747	1.132523
H	1.757035	1.135922	-1.513492
C1	-2.454118	2.190989	0.038066
C1	2.814452	1.939388	0.408117
C1	2.777693	-1.250968	-0.439811
C1	-0.049676	-2.671410	0.299802
C1	-2.563734	-0.812201	-1.146112
H	-1.615340	-0.563950	1.660488
O	-1.785381	-0.807859	2.605985
H	-1.396603	-1.684192	2.681959

TS 1→5: 1,2 (C3)

C	-0.135208	-1.721922	-0.1332050
C	-1.331169	-1.086092	-0.1617600
C	-1.428030	0.367805	-0.4460340
C	-0.096548	1.067526	-0.1318120
C	1.166853	0.322916	-0.5780820
C	1.119615	-1.071435	-0.2192940
H	-0.131328	-2.805498	-0.0632220
H	-0.038897	1.201410	0.9480770
H	1.484822	0.572461	-1.5905680
H	-1.771674	0.579080	-1.4612000
C1	-2.829083	-1.999128	-0.1504660
C1	2.479488	-2.044498	-0.8293230
C1	2.625866	1.259193	0.3659000
C1	-0.118725	2.725101	-0.8354140
C1	-2.700433	1.184040	0.5979370
H	1.290543	-0.915721	1.8242270
O	1.338082	-0.643586	2.7627150
H	1.917861	0.124124	2.7353110

post-reactive complex 1→5: 1,2 (C3)

C	0.694673	1.805509	-0.0331500
C	1.562774	0.796081	0.0198170
C	1.245769	-0.560636	-0.5632040
C	-0.259383	-0.835566	-0.6297100
C	-1.106788	0.371770	-0.8913080
C	-0.649940	1.577147	-0.5659450
H	0.974436	2.801120	0.2856200

H	-0.601215	-1.293661	0.2995820
H	-2.123531	0.209028	-1.2210220
H	1.686002	-0.599252	-1.5630800
Cl	3.190365	1.071365	0.5434270
Cl	-1.661871	2.988030	-0.7142810
Cl	-3.179775	-1.213952	1.3100310
Cl	-0.567734	-2.091826	-1.8943010
Cl	2.029709	-1.904125	0.3436670
H	-0.357638	0.791111	2.2834300
O	-0.490362	-0.112662	2.5828750
H	-1.359615	-0.374231	2.2282380

trans-1,3,5,6-tetrachlorocyclohexa-1,3-diene (**5**)

C	-1.145362	0.445918	0.3457530
C	-0.025441	1.477880	0.4211990
C	1.335722	0.879118	0.5497490
C	1.552536	-0.334299	0.0403110
C	0.507947	-1.121762	-0.6128570
C	-0.763255	-0.740658	-0.4800590
H	-0.233082	2.187577	1.2171600
H	-2.061764	0.906895	-0.0133180
H	0.782019	-2.003136	-1.1774850
H	2.125008	1.465276	1.0002730
Cl	-2.067135	-1.640627	-1.1756040
Cl	3.129102	-1.065783	0.1068820
Cl	-0.094822	2.467348	-1.1143560
Cl	-1.519206	-0.125279	2.0294770

pre-reactive complex **1**→**6**: 1,4 (C6)

C	0.176094	1.886169	-0.216300
C	-0.994394	1.216928	-0.178338
C	-1.170998	-0.200638	-0.180619
C	0.050612	-0.981268	-0.490288
C	1.316816	-0.306849	0.042355
C	1.441236	1.125928	-0.468364
H	0.233201	2.949527	-0.035489
H	0.170591	-1.239878	-1.545606
H	1.299483	-0.304747	1.132523
H	1.757035	1.135922	-1.513492
Cl	-2.454118	2.190989	0.038066
Cl	2.814452	1.939388	0.408117
Cl	2.777693	-1.250968	-0.439811
Cl	-0.049676	-2.671410	0.299802
Cl	-2.563734	-0.812201	-1.146112
H	-1.615340	-0.563950	1.660488
O	-1.785381	-0.807859	2.605985
H	-1.396603	-1.684192	2.681959

TS **1**→**6**: 1,4 (C6)

C	0.012430	1.838403	-0.6571520
C	-1.120259	1.115705	-0.3492850
C	-1.169597	-0.258278	-0.0817940
C	0.032581	-1.007260	-0.5750040
C	1.306126	-0.252652	-0.1927510
C	1.309862	1.215904	-0.6198810
H	-0.058224	2.893217	-0.8774340
H	-0.004177	-1.212440	-1.6512440
H	1.402738	-0.306713	0.8907760

H	1.965829	1.424450	-1.4583560
Cl	-2.619524	2.026329	-0.3187300
Cl	2.463226	2.086231	0.7660080
Cl	2.767966	-1.070625	-0.8556310
Cl	0.131039	-2.661026	0.1917870
Cl	-2.690295	-1.128714	-0.3563330
H	-0.905779	-0.349305	1.9357800
O	-0.648172	-0.526525	2.8640670
H	-0.332881	-1.435265	2.8424370

post-reactive complex 1→6: 1,4 (C6)

C	0.214366	-1.738392	-0.9947810
C	1.420576	-1.079627	-0.4855940
C	1.447898	0.226309	-0.2019480
C	0.243242	1.091460	-0.4993100
C	-1.072658	0.309091	-0.5349000
C	-0.943939	-1.086348	-1.0587710
H	0.297779	-2.774689	-1.2954020
H	0.418839	1.591320	-1.4549370
H	-1.511169	0.251721	0.4628640
H	-1.856901	-1.574511	-1.3734570
Cl	2.818457	-2.088006	-0.3033670
Cl	-3.788851	-1.485355	0.9267780
Cl	-2.266213	1.241950	-1.5221420
Cl	0.063778	2.441429	0.6888130
Cl	2.895573	1.034594	0.2783330
H	0.644580	-0.891820	2.4616990
O	-0.160531	-0.366979	2.5103980
H	0.147534	0.540455	2.6048150

trans-1,2,5,6-tetrachlorocyclohexa-1,3-diene (6)

C	-0.729852	0.462354	-0.2866140
C	-1.444167	-0.728654	0.3531300
C	-0.723679	-2.028436	0.1546120
C	0.601680	-2.048437	0.0428910
C	1.369916	-0.799082	0.0256520
C	0.772607	0.392048	-0.0937190
H	-1.304183	-2.940929	0.2008800
Cl	1.668243	1.853324	-0.2800920
Cl	3.091243	-0.963870	0.1021350
H	1.151325	-2.978205	-0.0257150
H	-1.565287	-0.545448	1.4241820
H	-0.938650	0.504728	-1.3591820
Cl	-3.119807	-0.834935	-0.3015390
Cl	-1.429222	1.972604	0.3962090

trans-1,2,5,6-tetrachlorocyclohexa-1,3-diene (7)

C	1.559623	0.691986	-0.3161630
C	1.559623	-0.691985	0.3161630
C	0.270238	-1.031824	0.9861090
C	-0.867243	-0.480525	0.5594980
C	-0.867243	0.480524	-0.5594980
C	0.270238	1.031824	-0.9861090
H	2.401581	-0.796663	0.9949200
H	2.401581	0.796663	-0.9949200
H	0.276750	1.753443	-1.7923000

H	0.276750	-1.753443	1.7923000
C1	-2.372263	0.877594	-1.3234440
C1	-2.372263	-0.877594	1.3234440
C1	1.874966	-1.911080	-1.0068410
C1	1.874966	1.911080	1.0068410

pre-reactive complex 2→1,2,4-TCB

C	0.755968	0.658673	0.1814740
C	-0.697046	0.255315	0.3833110
C	-1.079657	-0.895403	-0.4792840
C	-0.187244	-1.783653	-0.9259670
C	1.222513	-1.641743	-0.5710090
C	1.666143	-0.505053	-0.0294260
H	1.082307	1.295297	0.9999790
H	-0.491318	-2.631330	-1.5265200
H	1.897528	-2.464252	-0.7699660
C1	3.339045	-0.261026	0.3686950
C1	-2.779102	-1.078183	-0.8014250
C1	-0.882679	-0.268446	2.1288770
C1	0.844533	1.718430	-1.3064570
H	-1.361194	1.161327	0.2980610
O	-2.267362	2.627868	0.4130290
H	-1.943050	3.204016	-0.2851360

TS 2→1,2,4-TCB

C	0.776901	0.616017	0.2287740
C	-0.697417	0.289224	0.3676800
C	-1.103757	-0.837776	-0.4923840
C	-0.243042	-1.717452	-1.0214680
C	1.169440	-1.642644	-0.6684370
C	1.646780	-0.560334	-0.0471140
H	1.118776	1.186019	1.0889340
H	-0.579527	-2.517497	-1.6682670
H	1.816314	-2.474841	-0.9159650
C1	3.323002	-0.421565	0.4050510
C1	-2.821970	-1.019426	-0.7680040
C1	-0.999041	-0.199962	2.1148350
C1	0.976305	1.783083	-1.1911210
H	-1.377071	1.342712	0.2476760
O	-2.090006	2.514599	0.2445100
H	-1.682914	3.048386	-0.4437040

post-reactive complex 2→1,2,4-TCB

C	0.818572	-0.254924	0.8757030
C	-0.563601	-0.239612	0.7468060
C	-1.197812	-1.095188	-0.1514380
C	-0.443196	-1.971726	-0.9217600
C	0.939237	-1.996894	-0.8021470
C	1.552545	-1.134005	0.0955850
H	1.306228	0.431971	1.5530920
H	-0.942582	-2.631906	-1.6189740
H	1.530398	-2.674109	-1.4043370
C1	3.289896	-1.128508	0.2358390
C1	-2.922044	-1.068982	-0.3489740
C1	-1.470247	0.893071	1.7003960
C1	1.401976	2.846600	-0.5204150

H	-1.982833	1.731154	-0.9448510
O	-1.387061	1.867776	-1.6869310
H	-0.542051	2.137709	-1.2823640

pre-reactive complex 4→1,2,3-TCB

C	0.830932	0.018842	0.0293690
C	0.041926	-1.217541	-0.2135350
C	-1.243220	-1.261166	-0.5495280
C	-2.042749	-0.018856	-0.7318130
C	-1.282427	1.243673	-0.5227810
C	0.003790	1.234738	-0.1872230
H	-2.573029	-0.016912	-1.6834100
H	-1.825040	2.175709	-0.6211060
H	-1.755912	-2.207806	-0.6670220
Cl	0.913157	-2.711398	0.0442440
Cl	0.825393	2.751090	0.0969620
Cl	-3.427182	-0.053603	0.4946060
Cl	2.260461	0.052547	-1.1155280
H	1.305540	0.004762	1.1054610
O	1.871370	0.024535	2.5406960
H	2.306878	-0.806992	2.7487450

TS 4→1,2,3-TCB

C	0.826919	0.018956	0.0363910
C	0.043829	-1.215310	-0.2242170
C	-1.240257	-1.260211	-0.5668510
C	-2.041058	-0.018742	-0.7444750
C	-1.279919	1.243224	-0.5394880
C	0.005278	1.233069	-0.1973320
H	-2.581842	-0.016857	-1.6898920
H	-1.820588	2.175831	-0.6426420
H	-1.750730	-2.207348	-0.6896330
Cl	0.912946	-2.711720	0.0320960
Cl	0.824282	2.752018	0.0854600
Cl	-3.419169	-0.053923	0.4951880
Cl	2.286908	0.053460	-1.0686210
H	1.280998	0.003831	1.1421180
O	1.805656	0.021214	2.5395590
H	2.253723	-0.808293	2.7293190

post-reactive complex 4→1,2,3-TCB

C	-1.128461	0.282034	-0.2880780
C	0.112846	0.924370	-0.2726970
C	1.294890	0.195100	-0.2967380
C	1.244278	-1.192613	-0.3377470
C	0.021545	-1.850734	-0.3568050
C	-1.155440	-1.114156	-0.3312800
H	2.174159	-1.747581	-0.3528090
H	-0.031246	-2.931206	-0.3858870
H	2.252633	0.700805	-0.2784680
Cl	0.205931	2.656874	-0.1973340
Cl	-2.668569	-1.965270	-0.3280040
Cl	4.809826	-0.524664	-0.1718520
Cl	-2.595731	1.190820	-0.2133610
H	0.382801	-0.522521	2.2047900
O	-0.301261	-0.331585	2.8554530

H	-0.480971	0.607266	2.7481740
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pre-reactive complex 5→1,2,4-TCB

C	-0.922200	0.056553	0.3944780
C	-0.088718	1.323252	0.5148870
C	1.384769	1.098937	0.5867970
C	1.888489	0.009871	0.0034920
C	1.060773	-0.994079	-0.6611530
C	-0.260269	-0.962358	-0.4674390
H	-0.450529	1.925133	1.3444960
H	1.533528	-1.751883	-1.2719840
H	2.013160	1.844987	1.0544870
Cl	-1.294480	-2.172622	-1.1601770
Cl	3.605246	-0.287377	-0.0098080
Cl	-0.437385	2.346336	-0.9726870
Cl	-1.093245	-0.664673	2.0680980
H	-1.974598	0.305220	0.0900960
O	-3.643432	0.770776	-0.1790760
H	-3.613480	1.549007	-0.7430990

TS 5→1,2,4-TCB

C	-0.873030	0.047730	-0.0595090
C	-0.083552	1.226743	-0.6161070
C	1.385100	1.169795	-0.3077000
C	1.964774	-0.016809	-0.1481610
C	1.224830	-1.278082	-0.1699770
C	-0.109280	-1.239178	-0.1831270
H	-0.221883	1.310588	-1.6977390
H	1.766065	-2.213065	-0.1214730
H	1.954037	2.089873	-0.3322890
Cl	-1.009070	-2.718673	-0.0605440
Cl	3.687820	-0.146191	0.0880240
Cl	-0.775068	2.776713	0.0313340
Cl	-2.469099	-0.010567	-0.9045390
H	-1.130591	0.156264	1.0510910
O	-1.436943	0.129168	2.6794740
H	-2.313040	-0.159984	2.9494380

post-reactive complex 5→1,2,4-TCB

C	0.268084	-1.126634	-0.4970400
C	-0.705361	-1.182807	-1.4866310
C	-1.974166	-0.673247	-1.2513160
C	-2.254111	-0.111809	-0.0128390
C	-1.299451	-0.053647	0.9902110
C	-0.031339	-0.560981	0.7391620
H	-0.463855	-1.623082	-2.4454830
H	-1.526200	0.388034	1.9514170
H	-2.733142	-0.714137	-2.0213590
Cl	1.163622	-0.457469	1.9923510
Cl	-3.842251	0.536518	0.2965810
Cl	1.068512	2.460493	-0.8529240
Cl	1.853048	-1.748072	-0.8390380
H	3.505857	0.250860	0.4594470
O	3.766730	1.121778	0.1466620
H	2.931726	1.523867	-0.1550780

pre-reactive complex 5→1,3,5-TCB

C	-0.922200	0.056553	0.3944780
C	-0.088718	1.323252	0.5148870
C	1.384769	1.098937	0.5867970
C	1.888489	0.009871	0.0034920
C	1.060773	-0.994079	-0.6611530
C	-0.260269	-0.962358	-0.4674390
H	-0.450529	1.925133	1.3444960
H	1.533528	-1.751883	-1.2719840
H	2.013160	1.844987	1.0544870
Cl	-1.294480	-2.172622	-1.1601770
Cl	3.605246	-0.287377	-0.0098080
Cl	-0.437385	2.346336	-0.9726870
Cl	-1.093245	-0.664673	2.0680980
H	-1.974598	0.305220	0.0900960
O	-3.643432	0.770776	-0.1790760
H	-3.613480	1.549007	-0.7430990

TS 5→1,3,5-TCB

C	-0.932546	0.589926	0.0043930
C	-0.828412	-0.900243	0.2421290
C	0.510932	-1.466739	-0.0186700
C	1.581149	-0.668557	-0.1125720
C	1.522358	0.761934	0.1567510
C	0.325302	1.347174	0.2534450
H	-1.771615	1.013721	0.5499180
H	2.441775	1.316731	0.2925410
H	0.606590	-2.542076	-0.1209650
Cl	0.168487	3.040938	0.6216040
Cl	3.162287	-1.313341	-0.5016100
Cl	-1.244298	-1.217223	2.0108340
Cl	-1.374888	0.869716	-1.7740390
H	-1.747532	-1.531364	-0.3805310
O	-2.726584	-2.240118	-0.9701180
H	-2.886229	-1.778567	-1.7983040

post-reactive complex 5→1,3,5-TCB

C	-1.401073	-1.211783	-0.1957800
C	-2.027644	0.001210	0.0610480
C	-1.402048	1.220271	-0.1712620
C	-0.108494	1.198217	-0.6775670
C	0.559498	0.012756	-0.9530380
C	-0.107226	-1.178198	-0.6992290
H	-1.901744	-2.150545	-0.0020930
H	1.580145	0.016600	-1.3088950
H	-1.904157	2.154633	0.0394200
Cl	0.718829	-2.680192	-0.9958380
Cl	0.712881	2.706985	-0.9525670
Cl	-3.647577	-0.005620	0.6981000
Cl	3.489901	0.004623	0.8667060
H	0.009573	0.060888	1.8728580
O	0.742244	-0.090184	2.4768190
H	1.541564	-0.053484	1.9203120

pre-reactive complex 6→1,2,3-TCB

C	0.652135	0.398878	-0.0743350
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C	1.306039	-0.861408	-0.6229730
C	0.549392	-2.116839	-0.3124630
C	-0.766518	-2.085869	-0.1111160
C	-1.496597	-0.816159	-0.1004570
C	-0.848921	0.354912	-0.1422750
H	1.088688	-3.054590	-0.3613290
C1	-1.685815	1.857776	0.0346290
C1	-3.223044	-0.926400	0.0477580
H	-1.334325	-2.995553	0.0378160
H	1.455303	-0.790457	-1.7037710
C1	2.998211	-0.988704	0.0361610
C1	1.334899	1.814166	-0.9747410
H	0.922126	0.574834	1.0356990
O	1.156942	0.833455	2.6117740
H	2.027214	0.490779	2.8343820

TS 6→1,2,3-TCB

C	0.524543	0.751476	0.3142490
C	1.441703	-0.426556	0.0250250
C	0.909693	-1.336720	-1.0302400
C	-0.402626	-1.416814	-1.2656940
C	-1.346971	-0.613912	-0.4873580
C	-0.926893	0.396749	0.2835360
H	1.616444	-1.956024	-1.5688230
C1	-1.987986	1.408414	1.1940560
C1	-3.020506	-1.035665	-0.6206920
H	-0.810907	-2.089480	-2.0092880
H	0.794485	1.221701	1.2563990
C1	1.580529	-1.390505	1.5810400
C1	0.823532	2.034544	-0.9526230
H	2.477406	-0.102602	-0.1735910
O	4.231642	0.179020	-0.5826130
H	5.148072	0.083500	-0.3111590

post-reactive complex 6→1,2,3-TCB

C	-0.261687	0.687457	0.7821760
C	-0.853183	-0.320931	1.5305290
C	-0.206051	-1.540604	1.6725420
C	1.028123	-1.754180	1.0719260
C	1.615038	-0.739317	0.3256470
C	0.979251	0.495463	0.1696840
H	-0.666511	-2.330588	2.2517360
C1	1.695877	1.743269	-0.7853430
C1	3.152480	-1.040050	-0.4212370
H	1.541692	-2.701107	1.1744250
H	-1.819463	-0.145267	1.9837300
C1	-3.886647	-0.748267	-0.6345420
C1	-1.109879	2.190393	0.6016400
H	-0.469537	-1.603667	-1.1827240
O	-1.001364	-1.202605	-1.8767900
H	-1.865316	-1.036726	-1.4566950

pre-reactive complex 6→1,2,4-TCB

C	0.524543	0.751476	0.3142490
C	1.441703	-0.426556	0.0250250
C	0.909693	-1.336720	-1.0302400

C	-0.402626	-1.416814	-1.2656940
C	-1.346971	-0.613912	-0.4873580
C	-0.926893	0.396749	0.2835360
H	1.616444	-1.956024	-1.5688230
Cl	-1.987986	1.408414	1.1940560
Cl	-3.020506	-1.035665	-0.6206920
H	-0.810907	-2.089480	-2.0092880
H	0.794485	1.221701	1.2563990
Cl	1.580529	-1.390505	1.5810400
Cl	0.823532	2.034544	-0.9526230
H	2.477406	-0.102602	-0.1735910
O	4.231642	0.179020	-0.5826130
H	5.148072	0.083500	-0.3111590

TS 6→1,2,4-TCB

C	0.527112	0.712904	0.3030830
C	1.461384	-0.435158	-0.0067800
C	0.887236	-1.445951	-0.9151520
C	-0.425879	-1.503418	-1.1856290
C	-1.356216	-0.648489	-0.4576630
C	-0.922621	0.372144	0.2949960
H	1.569349	-2.157049	-1.3701580
Cl	-1.975991	1.386021	1.2244500
Cl	-3.039974	-1.050814	-0.5802190
H	-0.839626	-2.215992	-1.8879150
H	0.808854	1.203886	1.2305390
Cl	1.871805	-1.275292	1.5832070
Cl	0.773819	2.029001	-0.9815270
H	2.619430	-0.042090	-0.3972070
O	3.828490	0.324556	-0.8234140
H	4.483783	-0.208959	-0.3655670

post-reactive complex 6→1,2,4-TCB

C	0.652665	-0.863840	0.9091200
C	1.562825	-0.925804	-0.1340720
C	1.156728	-0.884517	-1.4605370
C	-0.197405	-0.777047	-1.7428210
C	-1.127015	-0.707295	-0.7124170
C	-0.699795	-0.750072	0.6119520
H	1.883443	-0.934133	-2.2605260
Cl	-1.827249	-0.646102	1.9244740
Cl	-2.807642	-0.536681	-1.1054370
H	-0.539232	-0.739584	-2.7692480
H	0.982196	-0.893911	1.9393520
Cl	3.264094	-1.049402	0.2382300
Cl	-0.662393	2.762727	0.0500840
H	1.518770	2.438094	-0.0395630
O	2.487647	2.368469	-0.1185100
H	2.729866	1.614005	0.4257480

pre-reactive complex 7→1,2,4-TCB

C	-1.355467	-0.324227	0.2450490
C	-0.999732	1.143247	0.4112470
C	0.438446	1.384926	0.7274980
C	1.361590	0.512444	0.3188090
C	0.977753	-0.705771	-0.4167950

C	-0.294816	-1.105683	-0.4527370
H	-1.653627	1.612803	1.1412770
H	-0.579755	-2.014120	-0.9686140
H	0.716025	2.287603	1.2558010
C1	2.209653	-1.612210	-1.2398250
C1	3.039580	0.791083	0.6642890
C1	-1.391140	1.993681	-1.1648830
C1	-1.569755	-1.031484	1.9260760
H	-2.340049	-0.462202	-0.2379510
O	-3.913142	-1.059825	-0.9605870
H	-4.505838	-0.773309	-1.6604040

TS 7→1,2,4-TCB

C	-1.044599	1.023304	0.4666960
C	-1.360218	-0.425733	0.1501220
C	-0.209148	-1.161683	-0.4322640
C	1.028727	-0.692488	-0.4000240
C	1.342984	0.541018	0.3456130
C	0.382537	1.337222	0.7781690
H	-1.696545	1.400182	1.2336260
H	0.605619	2.219381	1.3477940
H	-0.410645	-2.100268	-0.9168590
C1	3.004989	0.915464	0.7100250
C1	2.314164	-1.547178	-1.2180480
C1	-1.742586	-1.259822	1.7855380
C1	-1.509413	2.061340	-1.0068040
H	-2.505490	-0.631147	-0.5631510
O	-3.538660	-0.906798	-1.1655110
H	-3.666962	-0.250260	-1.8292700

post-reactive complex 7→1,2,4-TCB

C	1.612866	-0.978338	0.0479730
C	1.029319	-1.811330	-0.8968030
C	-0.354904	-1.866790	-0.9777550
C	-1.139456	-1.096420	-0.1280740
C	-0.534918	-0.269175	0.8151990
C	0.849039	-0.210519	0.9126680
H	1.642996	-2.406034	-1.5605110
H	1.313693	0.456166	1.6258950
H	-0.833002	-2.505576	-1.7091080
C1	-1.479916	0.726124	1.8748550
C1	-2.866458	-1.161294	-0.2891660
C1	-0.526002	2.148391	-1.8267730
C1	3.350969	-0.883300	0.1527850
H	0.902795	2.466133	-0.1603070
O	1.544589	2.704382	0.5339090
H	1.709042	3.641033	0.3945930

1,2,3-TCB

C	0.000075	2.501454	0.0000020
C	1.204012	1.811413	0.0000000
C	1.200597	0.423019	0.0000010
C	-0.000009	-0.292191	-0.0000030
C	-1.200555	0.423084	-0.0000040
C	-1.203896	1.811483	0.0000030
H	0.000111	3.583663	0.0000050

H	2.148951	2.338394	0.0000010
H	-2.148811	2.338506	0.0000070
Cl	-2.724052	-0.410904	0.0000030
Cl	-0.000107	-2.021021	-0.0000010
Cl	2.724065	-0.411025	-0.0000010

1,2,4-TCB

C	-1.295519	-1.464675	0.0000010
C	-1.715276	-0.141097	-0.0000020
C	-0.807981	0.906901	-0.0000030
C	0.552349	0.619583	-0.0000030
C	0.991970	-0.703325	-0.0000010
C	0.064359	-1.738981	0.0000020
H	-2.017162	-2.270641	0.0000040
H	-1.144816	1.935177	-0.0000030
H	0.413999	-2.763395	0.0000050
Cl	2.683621	-1.085499	0.0000030
Cl	1.677748	1.939910	-0.0000020
Cl	-3.419689	0.217849	0.0000010

1,3,5-TCB

C	1.028999	-0.908413	0.0000000
C	-0.278144	-1.375881	0.0000020
C	-1.300791	-0.437000	0.0000020
C	-1.051995	0.928673	0.0000000
C	0.272132	1.344922	-0.0000010
C	1.330571	0.446629	-0.0000010
H	-0.492549	-2.435981	0.0000020
H	-1.862725	1.644419	0.0000000
H	2.355520	0.791299	-0.0000030
Cl	0.617548	3.051257	-0.0000030
Cl	-2.952341	-0.990767	0.0000030
Cl	2.334507	-2.060097	0.0000000

1,3-dichlorocyclohex-2-en-1-yl localized anion

C	1.244239	0.011737	-0.5240740
C	0.016589	-0.713527	-0.3104660
C	-1.138115	-0.098120	0.0241710
C	-1.304620	1.381212	0.2202870
C	-0.026159	2.115745	-0.2169640
C	1.242363	1.349493	0.1804830
H	-1.542558	1.603447	1.2680590
H	-0.037331	2.231571	-1.3050920
H	1.240405	1.226985	1.2796780
Cl	-2.661085	-1.024736	0.0491120
H	-2.154833	1.742976	-0.3689420
H	-0.014940	3.119675	0.2148430
H	2.126759	1.941143	-0.0744840
Cl	2.671020	-0.996244	0.1401850
H	0.007822	-1.788379	-0.4727440

TS 1,3-dichlorocyclohex-2-en-1-yl delocalized anion

C	0.201076	-0.008801	1.2140850
C	0.402194	-0.643979	0.0000000
C	0.201076	-0.008801	-1.2140850
C	-0.558338	1.281430	-1.2851480

C	-0.297818	2.089684	0.0000000
C	-0.558338	1.281430	1.2851480
H	-1.644177	1.118575	-1.3989630
H	0.748216	2.412748	0.0000000
H	-1.644177	1.118575	1.3989630
Cl	0.201076	-0.990796	-2.7112480
H	-0.249233	1.882178	-2.1484910
H	-0.916341	2.991545	0.0000000
H	-0.249233	1.882178	2.1484910
Cl	0.201076	-0.990796	2.7112480
H	0.779257	-1.664523	0.0000000

1,2-dichlorocyclohex-2-en-1-yl anion

C	0.494606	-1.645166	-0.1564110
C	-0.360613	-0.657447	0.1724640
C	-0.025768	0.615712	0.7239440
C	1.482448	0.793286	0.8246890
C	2.238527	0.149084	-0.3472800
C	1.966287	-1.353865	-0.3326910
H	0.148609	-2.665712	-0.2809280
H	1.814178	0.307323	1.7520100
H	1.871514	0.582153	-1.2847290
H	2.542313	-1.821934	0.4768810
Cl	-2.130398	-1.051660	0.0550900
Cl	-0.722898	1.981779	-0.3695570
H	1.725778	1.852957	0.9265570
H	3.313526	0.341592	-0.2913040
H	2.317196	-1.818019	-1.2608390